

LIFELONG LEARNING: MEANS OF REALITY

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Abstract:

Realism in lifelong learning depends upon the way it renders to the needy through the aid of technology. This has been a virtual foundation in making education system in an efficient and cost conscious learning way. Education is merely delivery of knowledge, skills and information to students. Lifelong learning and University continuing education are broad idea-areas in equipping and enriching students with quality education. Undertaking all learning activities of both formal and non-formal learning throughout life of human beings with motto to enhance knowledge, skill and competency with socio-economic perspective is termed as lifelong learning. Definition of education is thus: People more free to learn, work and make their knowledge and skills to become prosperous, tolerant and democratic. Being an educated person means he has access to optimal position of mind and able to perceive accurately, think clearly and act effectively to achieve goal of socio-economy on self-reliance. The process learning aims at:

- ✓ Facilitating of learning towards self-respect and self-help in tune with socio-economic position
- ✓ Action of a real live-instructor
- ✓ Learning for acquisition of specific knowledge, skills or abilities for reaping optimum gains

Technology and LLL:

Virtual learning at anytime and anyplace with social status can possible only on the availability of need resources for a person to make learning a reality. With advancement of communication technologies, university can offer learning under distance mode and in various points in time. For instance, e-learning is not shift from traditional opening learning but rather as a support to conventional learning process with the use of modern information technology resulting in convergence process of learning at the distance education. Open and distance learning is the most rapidly growing fields of education and its potential impact on education itself. Absorbing large number of new learners and increasing number of traditional universities offering their programmes through distance are twin motives of the information and communication technology.

Trend of today is that learn the best in highly customisable environments and look teacher to create and structure their learning experience. Along with comfortable working online, a crucial element for successful delivering virtual courses entails transforming the educational experience is meaningful to the information-age learner. The reinforcing new ways of learning among the new generation is squarely depends upon the following shifts from:

- ✓ Linear to hypermedia learning
- ✓ Instructions to creation and discovery
- ✓ Teacher as transmitter to the teacher facilitator
- ✓ Absorbing to lifelong learning

The services of LLL offered by the education institutions expect the adults with different level of background knowledge and skills of Information and Communication Technology. This enthral on friendly, easy to use and robust technology for which the didactics to be designed in a way to motivate learning process of the learner. The ways for achieving the means of LLL is as:

Smart Learning: Smart learning is based on (i) observation and seeing, auditory Learning based on (ii) auditory listening to instructions/information and (iii) hands-on work and engaging in activities. In all these a variety of teaching approach covering different students with an equal opportunity to learn effectively is a guiding factor. Smart.

Coaching: Good quality teaching is enough to convey the essence of translating information, experience and knowledge to students for their wisdom in the contemporary society. This would aid students to understand and retain wisdom and pass on to others.

Technology: As influential factor, the students must be imbibed use of technology on online and internet service as the world has become a global village and also complement established education practices in new ways. The learning organisations follow a strategy of enhancing the learners' intimacy through their ICT services as high sophistication but simple to use certainly personalise e-learning. This dramatic development in e-learning creates enthusiasm among learners to mould a feeling of compatibility which enhances visibility and image. This base of e-learning will upgrade to m-learning for becoming a reality now-a-days.

The service of personalisation of an individual involves software patterns and preferences in wide ranging from simple display of the end-user's name on a web page to complex navigation and product customization. "Personalisation of technology ranges from commonplace use of databases and dynamic page generation to esoteric pattern matching and machine learning algorithms and data mining." [1] Now-a-days, up-gradation of e-learning to m-learning is becoming a reality.

Continuing Education: It refers to any type of post-literacy/post-secondary education, used to either obtain additional certifications, or as credits required to maintain a license and links up to the lifelong education aspiring with a view of creating a learning society. There is no specific format or length for a continuing education programme - may take a week, weeks or even months. A common characteristic to all continuing education programs is a registration process. Almost anybody can take continuing education credits for personal or professional enrichment; fitness trainers, nurses, and safety instructors are examples of professionals who fall into the second category. Continuing education is aimed exclusively to adults who already possess a college or university degree and others who want to upgrade their academic pursuits and professional skills. The continuing education must be made a way of life to the people feed themselves. The principle of LLL motivates the people to strengthen their life-style learning opportunities in:

- ✓ Non-formal education and adult education (pre-schools, colleges and universities are involved in formal education; civil societies, and organizations and associations)
- ✓ Continuing education institutions (hospitals, industries, government bodies, professional groups and associations)

Need and Relevance of Continuing Education:

Continuing education as gain expertise is obvious measure for gaining edge in the competitive in today's job market to enhance the chances earning income. The following are the main reasons which are as:

- ✓ Having a college degree or technical certification speaks about awareness job with gen which impresses the employer and become base to win on securing an opportunity of employment.
- ✓ Simply high school diploma not sufficient in job market particularly in the ladder of corporate sector culture as the job market demands knowing how do to and what do to in well. This is main motto why continuing education is a must. Hence, one should ever look for an opportunity with the base of earning graduation. In such situation, the employer is inclined to admit as employee and send him for training if any necessary.
- ✓ Under the ample opportunity of continuing higher education system, one can develop new transferable skills useful in current ever-changing market environment. Thinking critically with technical savvy in do-way of job is a hallway of the applicant.

New Trend of Online Education:

In technical revolution era, gaining an education on line virtually affect learning of many people at home making away of classroom learning in which require more scarifies needed. In view of this, the online education programme is every need of customization suiting the desire and time of learners. It means those help the daytime job and pursue learning of night time learning on online. This approach resorts to time and less expensive. Online education is more common than ever as future depends upon it. It suits one's own study time in today's busy lifestyle without any deterring reasons, say relocation to new place, documentation, etc., possible to attend class from anywhere. Thus, online education is an asset for a motivated person.

Conclusion:

In modern era, continuing education as formative effect in mind is a way to face challenges and means of life-to-live. In today's tight job market, Gain of LLL with tenet online would ensure one to be knowledgeable with scope of earnings. But for this, many people would found much better due to comfort than the traditional way learning. This incredible convenience is made online education popular among the generation of old and young. Getting online education is a superb means for the working individual as per the latest report, trying to be successful in all possible aspects of his life, family, career and finances is subjective.

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